

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL
TEACHER SURVEY

The European Vocational Teacher Survey 2025-2026

Promoting collaborative leadership for
evidence-based policy making

Dr. Irene Psifidou ([0000-0002-5728-7730](tel:0000-0002-5728-7730)), Cedefop expert
ELNE, 14 May 2025, Brussels

50
YEARS
SHAPING LEARNING AND
SKILLS FOR EUROPE

CEDEFOP

European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training

Boosting collaborative leadership to advocate for data needs to inform policies

- Advocate for the need to collect:
 - comparable data on **teachers' CPD provision and demand** across Europe
 - comparable evidence on CPD's **effectiveness**, drivers and barriers
- Involve all concerned actors to **identify research gaps**:
 - 2 years Cedefop feasibility study (2020-2022)
 - Interviews with key stakeholders
 - Set up of tripartite advisory group

Boosting collaborative leadership to design and implement EVTS

- Set up EVTS Stakeholder Group to:
 - Design survey questionnaire
 - Define sampling strategy for a representative survey in initial VET
 - Get endorsement letters from ministries
 - Define incentives strategy and survey campaign
 - Disseminate findings
 - Co-shape evidence-based policies
- Incentivise schools and leaders to engage teachers

EVTS governance: an example of collaborative leadership

Scientific leader

Supported by international research team

National VET experts' network

Tripartite EVTS stakeholders' Group
Country representatives & EU social partners (ETUCE, EFEE)

The screenshot displays a calendar titled 'Events' with three entries for stakeholder group meetings. Each entry includes the date, meeting name, and event type (Virtual event).

Event	Date	Event Type
1st EVTS Stakeholder group meeting	13 MAY 2024	Virtual event
2nd EVTS Stakeholder group meeting	27 SEP 2024	Virtual event
3rd EVTS Stakeholder group meeting	05 FEB 2025	Virtual event

Objectives

CPD = continuing professional development

How will it be done?

Teachers in initial VET schools
at ISCED level 3

EU-23 MS

Random two-stage sampling
(VET schools-teachers)

14 000 interviews in total
(differentiated by country)

Number of survey targeted respondents

14,000 teachers
in total

EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

CEDEFOP
European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training

HOME ABOUT THIS SURVEY DATA PROTECTION FAQs CONTACT FOR SCHOOLS FOR EXPERTS LANGUAGES

Welcome to the European Vocational Teacher Survey!

[Click here to login and complete the survey](#)

Your participation in the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is critical to improving vocational education and

Supporting cooperative school leadership in VET

- ✓ Furnish robust comparative data on VET teachers' views and needs
- ✓ Support evidence-based policy making at all levels
- ✓ Secure EU funds and programmes for teachers' CPD
- ✓ Increase attractiveness of VET teaching profession
- ✓ Address teachers' shortages
- ✓ Improve access, quality and relevance of CPD
- ✓ Improve teachers' working conditions and wellbeing
- ✓ Encourage peer mentoring and coaching among teachers
- ✓ Improve students' learning outcomes

VET4YOUTH TEAM

PROMOTING INCLUSIVE EXCELLENCE FOR YOUNG PEOPLE

@RenaPsifidou

0000-0002-5728-7730

Thank you

www.cedefop.europa.eu

Follow us on social media

#VETtoolkit #VETTeachersTrainers #EVTS

© Cedefop, 2025

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.18480585](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18480585)

CEDEFOP

European Centre
for the Development
of Vocational Training